

Determining the drivers of groundwater drought in the Netherlands: a panel quantile analysis

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Abstract

This thesis employs quantile regression for panel data to analyze the spatial and distributional impacts of various factors on groundwater drought in the Netherlands. The analysis examines groundwater levels from over 17,000 monitoring wells across the country from 2002-2024, covering diverse geological and topographical regions. The quantile regression models reveal that temperature, evaporation, elevation, urban areas, geographic region, and soil types are significant predictors of groundwater levels during drought conditions. Importantly, the magnitude and direction of these drivers' effects vary depending on the groundwater level quantile analyzed, highlighting the importance of considering the entire conditional distribution rather than just the mean. The research contributes to groundwater management by identifying areas more resilient or vulnerable to drought conditions based on their geographic and environmental characteristics. The findings provide a foundation for developing location-specific strategies for groundwater conservation and drought management in the Netherlands. They suggest that policymakers should align land use planning with soil types, tailor management strategies to local characteristics, develop climate adaptation policies, foster inter-regional collaboration, and invest in data-driven decision making.

Key words: Groundwater, Drought, Netherlands, Quantile Regression model, Quantiles, Panel data, Drivers of drought, Land Use, Spatial Analysis, Topography, Soil types, Hydrology, Lagged data.

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1 Introduction

This thesis explores the critical challenge of groundwater drought in the Netherlands, a country where groundwater serves as a fundamental resource for sustaining ecosystems, agriculture, and human activities, especially given the constraints of surface water availability (Pronk et al., 2021). The increased frequency and severity of droughts driven by climate change pose a significant threat to groundwater availability and management (IPCC, 2022). Understanding the complex dynamics of groundwater drought is essential for developing effective strategies to mitigate its impacts and ensure the long-term resilience of water supplies.

Climate change is expected to significantly impact groundwater resources through changes in precipitation patterns, evaporation, and groundwater recharge and discharge (Srinivasulu et al., 2024; Brakkee et al., 2022). Higher temperatures can increase evapotranspiration, representing the total amount of water released into the atmosphere, while precipitation variability can directly influence groundwater recharge. These climate-driven changes, combined with increased groundwater abstraction for human use, can lead to groundwater depletion and drought (El Bouazzaoui et al., 2024).

Guermazi et al. (2019) also emphasized that groundwater is becoming an increasingly threatened yet critical resource for sustaining ecosystems and human activities as climate change leads to more extreme weather events and variability in precipitation. Groundwater is a vital freshwater resource, with 1.5-3 billion people relying on it as their primary drinking water source (Amanambu et al., 2020). In the Netherlands, two-thirds of all drinking water comes from groundwater. Climate and anthropogenic changes are expected to reduce renewable groundwater resources and increase the risk of water scarcity, particularly in arid regions. Proper management of groundwater resources is therefore essential for drought preparedness and adaptation.

Groundwater drought is characterized by prolonged periods of abnormally low groundwater levels, posing significant challenges regardless of the climate context, as articulated by Nygren et al. (2022). Determining groundwater drought severity requires combining various objective and subjective data (Karunakalage et al., 2024). Maintaining a proper groundwater level is crucial since groundwater drought can result in groundwater depletion, land subsidence, ecosystem damage, and reduced water availability for human activities.

While there is a growing body of research on the impacts of climate change on surface water resources, the effects on groundwater have received relatively less attention. Groundwater is often considered more resilient to short-term climate variability, but the long-term impacts of changing precipitation patterns, temperature increases, and human abstraction can lead to severe and prolonged groundwater droughts (Taylor et al., 2013). Analyzing the spatial and temporal patterns of groundwater drought, as well as the underlying drivers, is crucial for informing sustainable groundwater management policies.

The main research questions addressed in this thesis are as follows: What are the drivers of groundwater drought, and how do they differ across the different quantiles of the groundwater distribution? How do the impacts of drought conditions differ spatially across the Netherlands, particularly between the southeastern part and the rest of the

country? What is the impact of the different covariates?

Modeling the relationship between climate change and subsurface water is challenging, since groundwater is relatively sensitive to seasonal and even decadal climate variability. Full ecosystem recovery from drought can take multiple years, and predicting this recovery time is important for water management given the increased drought frequency (Karunakalage et al., 2024).

This study employs a quantile regression (QR) model for panel data to provide new insights into the relationships between groundwater drought and various explanatory variables, including precipitation and temperature. Unlike traditional regression methods that focus on the mean, the QR approach allows for the examination of these relationships across different quantiles of the groundwater distribution. This methodology enables a more comprehensive understanding of how factors influence groundwater levels under various conditions, from normal circumstances to extreme drought periods. This analysis is particularly valuable for understanding the dynamics of groundwater systems and their response to climate variability and change.

The rest of this thesis is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a review of the existing literature on groundwater drought, focusing on its drivers, impacts, and the various methodological approaches employed in previous studies. Section 3 details the data sources and describes the methodological framework, with particular emphasis on the QR model for panel data. The results are presented and analyzed in Section 4, highlighting key findings and their implications for groundwater management. Section 5 provides a discussion of these results, contextualizing them within the broader scientific literature and exploring their practical significance. Finally, Section 7 concludes the thesis by summarizing the main findings, discussing their implications for policy and practice, and offering recommendations for future research directions in the field of groundwater drought analysis and management.

2 Literature review

The 2018-2019 drought brought severe damage to western and central Europe, and monitoring groundwater status is a crucial component of drought management strategies (Philip et al., 2020; Toreti et al., 2019; Bartholomeus et al., 2023). Similar to or worse than the previous groundwater droughts, they are expected to become more frequent in the future due to intensifying human pressure on freshwater resources (Samaniego et al., 2018). The Netherlands was one of the countries most affected, as groundwater is a crucial water source (Learbuch et al., 2022). Much of the damage was related to deep declines in groundwater levels, causing severe harm to ecosystems and raising concerns about the sustainability of increased water use.

Recent studies, such as those conducted by Brakkee et al. (2022) on the groundwater drought during the period 2018-2019, have provided insights into the spatio-temporal development of groundwater drought in the Netherlands. They develop time series modeling techniques with predefined impulse-response functions to analyze a large dataset of groundwater level measurements from across the southeastern Netherlands. Their ap-

proach involved validating raw data, reconstructing short records, and simulating groundwater levels beyond observations. This allowed for mapping the drought’s evolution using a much larger data set than typical drought studies. By comparing simulated groundwater levels against 30-year historical records, they quantified drought severity and identified areas that experienced extreme, record-breaking drought conditions. The time series models enabled real-time monitoring and forecasting of the drought’s progression. Their findings confirm that the meteorological drought in 2018 caused extreme groundwater drought throughout the southeastern Netherlands, but the timing of drought onset and duration varied strongly in space (Brakkee et al., 2022).

However, different Dutch regions are impacted unequally by groundwater droughts due to land use and hydrological system effects. Understanding the influence of spatial factors and investigating the underlying geographical, geological, and hydrological factors is crucial. The study by Karunakalage et al. (2024) analyzed groundwater drought characteristics and climatic impacts in South Korea using a novel approach based on the groundwater deficit (GWD) derived from NASA’s GRACE satellite data. They quantified drought severity as the cumulative GWD over time, identifying 13 major drought events from 2002-2021, with the largest deficits in 2015 and 2019. This approach provides a quantitative framework to assess groundwater drought frequency, severity, onset, cessation, and recovery, highlighting the importance of groundwater monitoring for comprehensive drought assessment, especially in data-limited regions. The insights can inform policies on sustainable groundwater use and recharge in the face of increasing drought risks in the Netherlands.

Nygren et al. (2022) analyzed groundwater hydrographs from lowland post-glacial environments in Sweden and Finland to assess aquifer memory and response time to meteorological forcing. Their results showed that groundwater anomalies were sometimes more influenced by climate teleconnections than concurrent meteorological forcing, emphasizing the need for a holistic, multi-timescale approach to characterize and project groundwater drought development, which depends on initial hydrological conditions and varies by hydrogeological setting. These insights can help increase understanding of groundwater drought responsiveness in lowland post-glacial environments.

Existing literature on groundwater drought has relied on time series methods, which, while valuable, often fall short of fully capturing the spatial variability and complex drivers of drought impacts. Many past studies have relied on hydrological simulations and trend analysis of aggregated values, which can be insufficient and challenging, especially when trying to separate anthropocentric influences from climate change effects on groundwater drought (Abbas and Xuan, 2019). To better understand the spatial heterogeneity, additional methods are needed that can characterize the interactions between climate, land use, geology, and other factors influencing groundwater drought at a regional scale. QR is a promising method for groundwater drought analysis, as it allows estimating the full conditional probability distribution of groundwater levels, which is useful for drought risk. This is particularly useful for investigating trends associated with extreme wet and dry conditions that may be missed by traditional regression methods focused on aggregated values.

QR has been widely used in statistical literature but has received relatively less at-

tention in water resources analysis and environmental studies. The use of QR in this study aligns with recent trends in hydrological research, such as the work of [Villarini et al. \(2011\)](#), who applied QR to analyze trends in flood peaks. This thesis’ application of this method to groundwater drought analysis in the Netherlands represents a novel contribution to the field. Studies like [Abbas et al. \(2019\)](#) and [Abbas and Xuan \(2019\)](#) demonstrate how QR can be effectively applied to analyze spatial and temporal patterns of regional water resources, including drought trends ([Chen et al., 2024](#)). [Abbas et al. \(2019\)](#) demonstrates the application of QR to analyze long-term rainfall trends in two climatically-different regions: the Dee River catchments in the UK and the Beijing Metropolitan Area in China. They use QR to estimate trends at the 0.98 quantile representing heavy rainfall and the 0.02 quantile for severe drought conditions. The QR-derived trends are then spatially interpolated to show their regional patterns. QR is a flexible regression technique that can reveal the full picture of climatic trends, beyond just the mean. By focusing on specific quantiles, it enables targeted analysis of extreme conditions that are of most concern for water resource planning and climate change adaptation ([Tareghian and Rasmussen, 2013](#)).

Applying QR to panel data has proven especially challenging. The ”fixed effects” approach used by [Graham et al. \(2015\)](#) may be useful, as groundwater drought levels could be subject to fixed effects, leaving the structure of dependence between the regressors and the unobserved heterogeneity unrestricted. Employing QR for panel data could provide new insights into the interactions between climate, land use, and groundwater that influence drought, as well as their spatial variability.

In conclusion, while time series modeling techniques have been effectively used to analyze groundwater drought in the Netherlands, as demonstrated by [Brakkee et al. \(2022\)](#), there is still potential for gaining additional insights using QR methods.

3 Methodology

3.1 Introduction of the quantile regression model

This study employs QR for panel data as the primary technique, building on the approach used by [Graham et al. \(2015\)](#). As discussed in Section 2, QR is particularly well-suited for modeling groundwater level time series data. It allows for the estimation of the entire conditional distribution of the dependent variable, capturing the heterogeneity in the relationship across different quantiles of groundwater levels. This is crucial for understanding the behavior of groundwater levels under various conditions, including extreme droughts.

The QR model in this thesis is based on the linear model introduced by [Koenker and Bassett Jr \(1978\)](#). It can capture the non-Gaussian or heavy-tailed distributed relationships in the groundwater system by estimating different coefficients β for each quantile. The panel data structure arises from having N independent observations (groundwater monitoring wells) across the Netherlands, which are assumed to be independently and identically distributed (i.i.d.). The dataset spans T time periods, consisting of bi-monthly measurements over 20 years. This approach allows us to account for both spatial and

temporal variations in groundwater levels, providing an analysis of drought conditions across different locations and time scales.

The choice of QR is justified by its ability to model the conditional quantiles of the response variable, offering a more detailed exploration of the relationships between predictors and groundwater levels, particularly in extreme conditions. Traditional linear regression models focus on the mean of the dependent variable, potentially overlooking important variations in the tails of the distribution. QR, on the other hand, provides a more robust and flexible framework for understanding these variations, as demonstrated in studies like [Li et al. \(2015\)](#), who analyzed time series data using QR and created Quantile Autoregressive (QAR) models to account for dependencies on past values.

3.2 Set-up of the quantile regression model for panel data

Let $y_{i,t}$ be a 1×1 unit representing the groundwater level at a particular well i at time t , where $i = 1, \dots, N$ and $t = 1, \dots, T$.

The $k \times 1$ regressor vector $x_{i,t}$ represents the k explanatory variables for observation i at time t . These include the climate variables (temperature, precipitation, and evaporation), as well as spatial and geological variables (elevation, urban areas, and soil types).

$\beta(\tau)$ are the $k \times 1$ regression coefficients, where $\tau \in (0, 1)$ represents the quantile of interest. For instance, $\tau = 0.025$ corresponds to the 2.5th percentile, which is particularly informative for understanding extreme drought conditions.

The relationship between the dependent variable and regressors is expressed as:

$$y_{i,t} = x'_{i,t}\beta(\tau) + \alpha_i + \epsilon_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

where α_i represents well-specific fixed effects and $\epsilon_{i,t}$ is the error term.

Assuming $Q^\tau(\epsilon_{i,t}|x_{i,t}) = 0$, the QR model for panel data can be written as:

$$Q^\tau(y_{i,t}|x_{i,t}) = x'_{i,t}\beta(\tau) + \alpha_i, \quad (2)$$

where $Q_{y|x}(\tau|x_{i,t})$ is the τ 'th conditional quantile of the groundwater level for well i at time t . $\beta(\tau)$ are the QR coefficients that vary across τ , α_i captures the unobserved heterogeneity across wells (fixed effects), and ϵ is the error term.

The QR coefficients $\hat{\beta}(\tau)$ are estimated by solving the following optimization problem:

$$\hat{\beta}(\tau) = \arg \min_{\beta} \sum_{i=1}^n \rho_\tau(y_i - x'_{i,t}\beta(\tau) - \alpha_i) \quad (3)$$

where $\rho_\tau(u) = u(\tau - \mathbb{I}(u < 0))$ is the check function, with $\mathbb{I}(\cdot)$ being the indicator function.

3.3 The models

The study employs a series of pooled QR models to analyze groundwater drought using the 'quantreg' package in R developed by [Koenker and Bassett Jr \(1978\)](#). The pooled panel data QR model assumes that the model parameters are common across individual

wells and that there are no observable entity-specific effects. In other words, all entities in the dataset are considered to have the same underlying characteristics, and there is no dependence within the individuals ($\alpha_i = \alpha$). This approach is similar to a standard regression model, as described by [Schmidheiny \(2021\)](#).

The pooled QR model is specified as:

$$Q^\tau(y_{i,t}|x_{i,t}) = \alpha + x'_{i,t}\beta(\tau), \quad (4)$$

where $Q_{y|x}(\tau|x_{i,t})$ is the estimated τ 'th conditional quantile of the groundwater level for well i at time t . α is the intercept, $\beta(\tau)$ are the QR coefficients that may vary across τ , and $x_{i,t}$ are the regressors (independent variables) that potentially influence groundwater drought.

In the analysis, the focus will be on the lower tail of the groundwater level distribution, as it represents the levels during different types of drought conditions. The analysis primarily focuses on the 2.5th quantile of groundwater levels to capture extreme drought conditions, with additional quantiles (10th, 25th, and 50th) on the left side of the distribution also examined. These quantiles were chosen for the following reasons: The 2.5th quantile represents extreme drought, which is crucial for analyzing factors with the most significant impact during severe water scarcity. The 10th quantile captures moderate drought conditions, allowing us to understand how the influence of various factors changes as drought severity decreases. The 25th quantile represents mild drought or below-average conditions, providing insights into factors affecting groundwater levels during less severe dry periods. Finally, the 50th quantile (median) represents typical conditions, serving as a baseline for comparing drought impacts with normal groundwater levels ([Koenker, 2005](#)).

Six models are constructed, progressively incorporating different sets of variables to identify key drivers of groundwater drought. The initial temporal model includes only year dummies (2003-2023, with 2002 as the baseline) to capture temporal variations and identify years with significant drought impacts. Model 1, the climate Model, incorporates primary climate variables (temperature, precipitation, and evaporation) to assess their direct impact on groundwater levels. Model 2, the topographic model, adds elevation to explore topographic influences, while Model 3, the spatial model, introduces dummy variables for urban areas and the southeast region to capture land use and regional effects. Model 4 incorporates all previous variables plus soil type information (sand, dunes, peat, hills, river clay, and sea clay), providing the most complete picture of factors influencing groundwater levels during drought conditions.

The inclusion of interaction terms in Model 5 allows for a more nuanced understanding of how different variables work together to influence groundwater levels. By incorporating an interaction term between urban areas and elevation, the model can explore how the impact of elevation on groundwater levels differs in urban versus non-urban settings. This is particularly important given that urbanization significantly alters hydrological processes, affecting both infiltration and evapotranspiration ([Salvadore et al., 2015](#)). In urban areas, increased impervious surfaces can lead to higher runoff and reduced groundwater recharge, while in rural areas, higher elevation might correlate with better infiltration and groundwater availability. Additionally, the interaction term between temperature

and precipitation helps model how temperature modifies the effectiveness of precipitation in replenishing groundwater, especially under varying seasonal dynamics. This interaction is crucial as higher temperatures can increase evapotranspiration rates, thereby reducing the amount of precipitation that actually recharges groundwater.

Model 6 further refines the analysis by incorporating time lags for precipitation to capture its delayed impact on groundwater levels. The approach of adding lags for precipitation in the model is supported by studies like [Schreiner-McGraw and Ajami \(2021\)](#) and [Li et al. \(2015\)](#), which demonstrate the importance of considering delayed responses in groundwater systems. Using time lags for precipitation in the groundwater levels model is crucial due to the delayed response of groundwater systems to meteorological changes ([Schreiner-McGraw and Ajami, 2021](#)). This delay can vary widely depending on factors such as soil type, land cover, and local hydrological conditions. In areas with highly permeable soils, groundwater levels may respond to precipitation within days or weeks, while in regions with less permeable soils or significant surface runoff, the lag can extend to several weeks or months. For the given groundwater monitoring wells, the response to precipitation will be observed using time lags of two weeks, one month, three months, six months and one year.

However, it is important to note that the relationship between precipitation and groundwater levels can extend over much longer time scales. [Schreiner-McGraw and Ajami \(2021\)](#) demonstrated a significant time-lag of up to 15 years between the initiation or termination of a precipitation drought and the corresponding groundwater drought in unconfined aquifers not impacted by anthropogenic groundwater management. This highlights the potential for long-term hydrological memory in groundwater systems.

By systematically adding the variables to the QR model, it can be assessed how different factors affect the model’s explanatory power and identify the primary contributors to groundwater drought. This process will involve evaluating the significance and contribution of each predictor variable to the model fit at the selected quantiles.

3.4 Goodness of fit

The QR models are tested for their goodness of fit based on two complementary methods. First, the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) is employed to assess the relative quality of the model for the given dataset ([Akaike, 1973](#)). Additionally, to assess the improvement in model fit compared to a baseline model without any explanatory variables, the AIC difference is calculated between the improved model and the baseline model:

$$\Delta \text{AIC} = \text{AIC}(\text{nullmodel}) - \text{AIC}(\text{improved model})$$

By penalizing model complexity, AIC strikes a balance between goodness of fit and simplicity, preventing overfitting and promoting models that generalize well ([Shin et al., 2022](#)). A lower AIC value indicates a better balance between goodness-of-fit and model complexity.

The AIC for a QR model is calculated as:

$$\text{AIC} = -2\frac{\ell}{n} + 2\frac{k}{n}, \quad (5)$$

where:

- ℓ is the pseudo log-likelihood of the model
- n is the number of observations
- k is the number of parameters (including the intercept) in the model

Secondly, the models are evaluated for their goodness-of-fit using the pseudo- R^2 measure. [Koenker and Machado \(1999\)](#) introduced a goodness-of-fit measure for QR that is analogous to the conventional R^2 statistic used in least squares regression. In linear least squares regression, the R^2 can be described as the fraction of the variation in the response that is explained by the model. In the QR model, the pseudo- R^2 is defined as:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \rho_\tau(y_i - x_i' \hat{\beta}_\tau)}{\sum_{i=1}^n \rho_\tau(y_i - \hat{Q}_\tau(y|x_i))} \quad (6)$$

where:

- ρ_τ is the check function
- $\hat{\beta}_\tau$ are the estimated QR coefficients
- $\hat{Q}_\tau(y|x_i)$ is the estimated conditional quantile function

The pseudo- R^2 ranges from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating a better fit of the model to the data. This measure provides an understanding of the model's performance.

3.5 Data

The analysis will use a panel data set covering various factors influencing groundwater levels and drought conditions in the Netherlands. The data are gathered from different sources, and all variables will be introduced separately.

3.5.1 Groundwater levels

The groundwater level time series used in this study is obtained from the Droogteportaal (Drought Portal), which consolidates groundwater level measurements from multiple institutions across the Netherlands. The dataset spans from 2002 to 2024, providing a robust temporal range for long-term analysis, as recommended by [Brakkee et al. \(2022\)](#).

The groundwater levels are measured in meters relative to the Normaal Amsterdams Peil (NAP), a reference date where 0 m NAP corresponds to the average sea level of the North Sea. [Figure 1](#) shows the locations of 17,122 groundwater monitoring wells throughout the Netherlands, primarily concentrated in the southeastern part of the country.

To prepare the data for the analysis, the raw observations were cleaned to create a consistent panel dataset with daily groundwater level readings. This process involved removing rows with missing values and outliers, as well as filtering out deeper wells with different filter levels that respond differently to precipitation and evaporation.

Observations from the 14th and 28th of each month will be utilized, as these were the days when most measurements were conducted. The large number of missing values can

Figure 1: Groundwater well locations in the Netherlands (source: Droogteportaal)

be avoided by including only the 14th and 28th of each month, decreasing the running time of the QR model but leading to a less accurate representation. However, bimonthly observations will suffice for the analysis of groundwater drought.

For this research, the raw data is used in the subsequent modeling and analysis.

3.5.2 Climate variables

To assess the impact of climate variability on groundwater recharge and drought, the independent variables precipitation, evaporation, and temperature will be included. These climatic variables are crucial in determining the drivers of groundwater levels.

The data are obtained from the Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut (KNMI - Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute), which manages automatic weather stations across the Netherlands that continuously measure various meteorological parameters (KNMI, 2023). The data are gathered from 60 different weather stations, providing coverage from north to south. Figure 2 shows the locations of the weather stations.

The average daily temperature (in $0.1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) exhibits a clear seasonal pattern, with higher mean temperatures observed during summer months and lower mean temperatures during winter months, typical of the temperate climate in the Netherlands. The temperature data of De Bilt, which is in the centre of the Netherlands, in Figure 3 shows cyclical behavior, with peaks occurring around July-August and troughs around

Figure 3: Average temperature in De Bilt (in 0.1 degrees Celcius)

Figure 4: Precipitation in De Bilt (in 0.1 mm)

Figure 5: Evaporation in De Bilt

3.5.3 Land use types

Additional information on land use, geographical location, geology type, and elevation will be incorporated to better understand the spatial variability in groundwater dynamics across different regions of the Netherlands. According to [Brakkee et al. \(2022\)](#), these factors may influence groundwater levels and patterns.

Land use and land cover change are the result of complex interactions between different biophysical and socioeconomic conditions that vary across space and time [Verburg et al. \(2002\)](#). The Netherlands, with a total land and water area of 4.2 million hectares, exhibits diverse land use patterns. In 2015, agriculture was the dominant land use, occupying approximately half of the country’s surface area and spanning around 2.1 million hectares dedicated to croplands, pastures, and other farming activities [Statistics Netherlands \(2020\)](#). Concurrently, roughly one-third, or 1.4 million hectares, were classified as nature areas, water bodies, or spaces designated for recreational purposes, encompassing forests, wetlands, lakes, rivers, and leisure spaces. A relatively small part of the Dutch territory was earmarked for buildings, roads, and other infrastructure, reflecting the nation’s balanced approach to urban development and the preservation of natural and agricultural landscapes.

The land use data used for this analysis is extracted from the Landelijk Grondgebruik Nederland (LGN), a detailed land use map of the Netherlands for the year 2022. The LGN2022 map was created by Wageningen Environmental Research using satellite imagery and additional datasets, providing an up-to-date and accurate representation of land use in the Netherlands (see [Figure 6](#)). The study area is geographically bounded by 53.67°N to the north, 50.66°N to the south, 7.38°E to the east, and 3.16°W to the west. It

distinguishes between 51 land use classes, including the main agricultural crops, forests, water bodies, nature areas, and urban areas.

Figure 6: LGN2022 land use map of the Netherlands

3.5.4 Geology

The geology of an area plays a crucial role in determining groundwater availability, flow patterns, and susceptibility to drought. The geology type data for the Netherlands was obtained from the Dinoloket website [DINoloket \(2023\)](#), which provides detailed information about the subsurface models of the country.

Figure 7 presents the geology map of the Netherlands, illustrating the spatial distribution of different geological formations. The map reveals a diverse geological landscape, with varying rock types, sediment layers, and aquifer systems across the country. The northeastern part of the Netherlands is dominated by sandy and gravelly sediments deposited by glaciers and meltwater during the Pleistocene epoch. Central and western parts of the country are characterized by younger Holocene deposits, including peat and clay layers formed in coastal and estuarine environments. The southeastern region features a mix of sandy and loamy sediments, as well as some areas with chalk and limestone bedrock.

The geology data was integrated with the groundwater well information to analyze

Figure 7: Geology map of the Netherlands (source:DINOloket)

the relationship between well characteristics and the underlying geology. For example, sandy and gravelly aquifers in the northeast may be more susceptible to rapid water table declines during drought periods due to their high permeability and limited storage capacity. In contrast, clay and peat layers in the central and western parts of the country may help to buffer groundwater levels by slowing recharge and discharge processes. The varied geology in the southeast likely leads to a mix of groundwater drought responses, depending on the local hydrogeological conditions.

3.5.5 Elevation

Elevation is a crucial factor in determining groundwater levels and susceptibility to drought. The Netherlands exhibits a diverse topography, with a significant portion situated in low-lying areas and only the southernmost part and some central regions at higher elevations, as shown in Figure 8.

The areas with higher elevations, particularly in the east and south of the country, are more susceptible to groundwater drought. These upland regions are characterized by elevated sandy soils with limited access to surface water resources. This makes them heavily dependent on precipitation for groundwater recharge and particularly vulnerable to drought conditions, especially during periods of low rainfall.

However, the relationship between elevation and groundwater drought is not straightforward, especially in urban areas. The urban landscape influences infiltration and evapotranspiration, complicating our capacity to quantify their dynamics across a heterogeneous landscape at contrasting scales [McGrane \(2016\)](#). Urban development can

(a)

(b)

Figure 8: Elevation map of the Netherlands with legend (Source: Esri, AHN)

significantly alter natural hydrological processes, affecting how elevation interacts with groundwater levels. For instance, impervious surfaces in cities can reduce infiltration and increase runoff, potentially exacerbating drought conditions even in areas where elevation might otherwise be favorable for groundwater retention.

To capture this complex interplay between urban development and elevation in relation to groundwater levels, incorporating an interaction term between urban areas and elevation values in the QR model can provide valuable insights into how urbanization modifies the elevation-groundwater relationship across different drought intensities.

In contrast, the lower-elevation areas, primarily in the western parts of the Netherlands, tend to be less affected by groundwater drought. These areas benefit from more advanced water management capabilities and proximity to major rivers. They often have deeper groundwater tables that can be more effectively regulated and can act as water

storage zones during wetter periods, helping to mitigate the impacts of dry spells.

3.6 The complete panel data set

Integrating climate data into groundwater analyses requires associating each monitoring well with a nearby meteorological station. An algorithm implemented in R matches well coordinates from the Drought Portal dataset with weather station locations. The Vincenty great-circle distance [Vincenty \(1975\)](#) is calculated between each well and every station, identifying the nearest station and its distance in kilometers for each well. This produces a dataset linking each groundwater well to its closest climate observation point, allowing the addition of corresponding climate values for temperature, precipitation, and evaporation to the panel dataset.

To explore relationships between land use and groundwater, wells are categorized by land cover type based on their spatial coordinates. Spatial analysis tools in R extract land use values at each well location from the LGN2022 dataset. The primary land use types are incorporated as covariates in the QR model.

The LGN2022 dataset is broadly grouped into rural (agricultural fields, grasslands, forests) and urban (residential, industrial, built-up) categories based on the spatial land use codes. Elevation data is added to the panel dataset using the same spatial algorithm, assigning values to each well based on its coordinates.

To account for geological influences, wells are classified into six major types based on dominant features: sand, dune, hill, peat land, river clay, and sea clay. These geological categories are incorporated as dummy variables in the panel data, with each well assigned a value of 1 for its corresponding type and 0 otherwise. Including these six dummies in the model allows the analysis to capture the potential impact of different geological formations on groundwater levels.

Spatial differences between the southeastern Netherlands and the rest of the country are investigated by incorporating a dummy variable for the southeastern region. Wells situated within the latitude and longitude bounds of the southeastern region of the Netherlands are coded as 1, while those outside these bounds are coded as 0. Notably, 30.47% of the total wells (445,208) are located in the southeastern part of the Netherlands, providing a relatively large amount of information about the groundwater levels in this region.

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the full panel dataset, including the mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values for each variable, along with their respective units.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of the Full Panel Data

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Unit
Groundwater Level	7.7	7.7	-15.8	29.5	m NAP
Temperature	10.3	6.3	-8.1	26.2	°C
Precipitation	2.3	5.5	-0.1	131.6	mm
Evaporation	16.6	13.7	0.0	56.0	Makkink
Sand	-	-	-	-	-
Dunes	-	-	-	-	-
Peat	-	-	-	-	-
Hills	-	-	-	-	-
River Clay	-	-	-	-	-
Sea Clay	-	-	-	-	-
Urban	-	-	-	-	-
Southeast	-	-	-	-	-
Elevation	1.1	1.0	-0.5	9.8	m

4 Results

This section presents the findings from the methodology described in Section 3. The analysis focuses on the three key aspects: temporal differences, spatial variations, and the impact of land use and geology. The results are organized in the tables in Section 4.2 to facilitate the comparison of the effect of the inclusion of different variables in the QR model during different drought conditions.

The hypothesis is that the impact of drought conditions is larger in the east and the south of the Netherlands than in the rest of the Netherlands. Strong regional differences were observed in the precipitation shortfall across the country, with highest deficits in the southern and eastern regions (Philip et al., 2020).

4.1 Temporal model results

To investigate the temporal dynamics of drought’s impact on groundwater levels, a QR model was fitted with year dummies for each year from 2003 to 2023, using 2002 as the baseline. The QR results at the 2.5th percentile, displayed in Table 2, reveal the temporal differences in drought severity. Years with large negative coefficients, indicating significantly lower groundwater levels compared to the baseline, are likely to have experienced more severe drought conditions. For example, 2012-2016 and 2018-2020 stand out as the most severe drought years, with 2013 having the largest negative coefficient of -1.29437. In the early 2000s, 2003 had the largest negative coefficient (-0.76537). It is important to note that these year dummies were created for the whole calendar year, which may not capture the specific effects of drought during different seasons and could lead to insufficient information about the temporal dynamics of drought impact.

Additional QR models were estimated for other quantiles on the left side of the dis-

Table 2: Temporal QR results for groundwater levels at 2.5th percentile

	Value	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-1.45963	0.04146	-35.20455	0.00000
year2003	-0.76537	0.08085	-9.46695	0.00000
year2004	-0.27537	0.09821	-2.80394	0.00505
year2005	0.15963	0.12864	1.24091	0.21464
year2006	0.38963	0.11410	3.41490	0.00064
year2007	0.21363	0.05257	4.06392	0.00005
year2008	0.19363	0.05362	3.61082	0.00031
year2009	-0.03437	0.04906	-0.70069	0.48350
year2010	-0.06937	0.04499	-1.54185	0.12311
year2011	-0.71737	0.06211	-11.54952	0.00000
year2012	-1.08037	0.04767	-22.66513	0.00000
year2013	-1.29437	0.05041	-25.67663	0.00000
year2014	-1.26337	0.05098	-24.78164	0.00000
year2015	-0.92137	0.05488	-16.78846	0.00000
year2016	-0.87037	0.04784	-18.19523	0.00000
year2017	-0.55237	0.04636	-11.91498	0.00000
year2018	-0.74337	0.04567	-16.27694	0.00000
year2019	-0.71937	0.04728	-15.21659	0.00000
year2020	-0.61337	0.04450	-13.78408	0.00000
year2021	-0.39638	0.05897	-6.72215	0.00000
year2022	-0.52812	0.04459	-11.84435	0.00000
year2023	-0.30937	0.04314	-7.17132	0.00000

tribution, as shown in Table 3. The results show the temporal differences in drought situations across various groundwater level quantiles.

4.2 General model results

The results of the QR models across the different quantiles are presented in Tables 4, 5, 6 and 7. By comparing the models across quantiles, we gain insight into the effect of the explanatory variables changing under different groundwater level conditions, particularly drought conditions.

In general, adding more parameters in the model decreases the AIC, which indicates a better model fit. Under extreme drought conditions (2.5th quantile), the full model with interactions (Model 5) demonstrates the best fit with the lowest AIC of 9,351,341, indicating an optimal balance between goodness-of-fit and model complexity (Table 4). The improvement in fit is clear from the Δ AIC of 776,479.2 between the null model and Model 5. The pseudo- R^2 value of 0.9037133 for Model 5 indicates a very strong explanatory power, representing a substantial improvement over the simpler models.

In this model, all variables except precipitation are statistically significant predictors

Table 3: Temporal QR results for groundwater levels across quantiles

Variable	Quantile 0.1	Quantile 0.25	Quantile 0.5 (Median)
(Intercept)	-0.13000***	2.47600***	7.62900***
year2003	0.21200	3.23400***	1.48900***
year2004	1.28500***	2.92300***	1.89300***
year2005	1.98500***	3.48900***	1.81100***
year2006	1.75300***	2.72700***	1.12200***
year2007	1.26200***	2.43500***	1.04800***
year2008	1.27400***	2.43900***	0.96900***
year2009	0.91500***	2.04400***	0.74700***
year2010	0.29900***	1.06800***	0.28800***
year2011	-0.15700***	0.24600**	-0.01300
year2012	-0.54700***	-0.78600***	-1.18700***
year2013	-0.71500***	-1.09700***	-1.66407***
year2014	-0.79400***	-1.46000***	-2.10800***
year2015	-0.64500***	-1.38300***	-2.03100***
year2016	-0.68871***	-1.35217***	-1.95200***
year2017	-0.63317***	-1.43700***	-2.18900***
year2018	-0.74708***	-1.58900***	-2.49100***
year2019	-0.69200***	-1.44900***	-2.38958***
year2020	-0.66400***	-1.52400***	-2.42200***
year2021	-0.40000***	-1.20400***	-2.17200***
year2022	-0.54400***	-1.31000***	-2.09800***
year2023	-0.40400***	-1.03721***	-1.60300***

*** p < 0.001 ** p < 0.01 * p < 0.05

of groundwater levels during extreme drought conditions. The intercept values across models range from -2.26531 to -1.35871, indicating the baseline groundwater level when all other variables are zero. These negative values suggest that, under extreme drought conditions, groundwater levels are low.

The coefficients from the quantile regression models at the 2.5th quantile reveal the relative impacts of various covariates on groundwater levels during extreme drought conditions. The coefficient for temperature ranges from -0.00130 to -0.00164, indicating that for each one-unit increase in temperature, groundwater levels decrease by approximately 0.0013 to 0.0016 units in the extreme drought case. Evaporation has a significant negative coefficient in Model 1 of -0.00435, suggesting that each unit increase in evaporation results in a decrease of about 0.0044 units in groundwater levels, highlighting its substantial impact during droughts. Conversely, elevation shows a positive influence with coefficients between 0.00215 and 0.00261, meaning that for each unit increase in elevation, groundwater levels rise by approximately 0.0022 to 0.0026 units. The urban variable has a negative coefficient of -0.51347 in Model 3, indicating that urbanization is associated with a decrease of about 0.513 units in groundwater levels. Among the soil types, sand

has a positive coefficient of 0.23607, suggesting that sandy soils contribute to an increase of about 0.236 units in groundwater levels, while peat land exhibits a dramatic negative coefficient of -7.65426, indicating a decrease of over 7.65 units in groundwater levels, likely due to high water retention and low recharge capacity. River clay also has a negative coefficient of -1.23795, suggesting a decrease of approximately 1.24 units in groundwater levels. In contrast, sea clay presents a significant positive coefficient of 8.97799, indicating that areas with sea clay are associated with an increase of nearly 9 units in groundwater levels.

For the 10th quantile, representing moderate drought conditions, Model 5 again demonstrates the best fit with the lowest AIC (Table 5). In Model 5, all variables except evaporation are statistically significant predictors of groundwater levels during a moderate drought. Temperature (-0.00144) and urban areas (-0.57197) maintain negative coefficients, as do peat lands (-1.04693) and river clay (-0.78842). Conversely, precipitation (0.00096), elevation (0.00423), southeast region (0.36371), sand (1.16420), dunes (0.08439), hills (0.86897), and sea clay (7.33351) exhibit positive coefficients. Notably, evaporation loses its statistical significance in this model, which may suggest potential covariation with temperature. The pseudo- R^2 value of 0.7414128 for Model 5 indicates strong explanatory power, representing a substantial improvement over the simpler models.

The model selection results for the 25th and 50th quantiles, representing wetter conditions, follow a similar pattern to the lower quantiles. For both quantiles, the full model (Model 5) demonstrates the best fit with the lowest AIC values (7,843,204 for the 25th quantile and 6,962,966 for the 50th quantile) (Tables 6 and 7). At the 25th quantile, all variables are statistically significant predictors of groundwater levels, which is the only estimated model that has this. The coefficient signs are consistent with the 10th quantile results, with temperature (-0.00175), urban areas (-0.7586), peat lands (-0.20868), and river clay (-1.16416) showing negative associations, while precipitation, elevation, southeast region, sand, dunes, hills, and sea clay exhibit positive associations. For the 50th quantile (median), all variables are statistically significant predictors. The coefficient signs are largely consistent with the 10th and 25th quantile results. The pseudo- R^2 values for Model 5 (0.6127993 for the 25th quantile and 0.6640333 for the 50th quantile) indicate strong explanatory power, with substantial improvements over the simpler models across both quantiles.

Overall, the QR model selection results suggest that the full model (Model 5) is the preferred model across all quantiles, with the majority of variables being statistically significant predictors of groundwater levels. The coefficient signs indicate that temperature, urban areas, peat lands, and river clay are negatively associated with groundwater levels, while precipitation, elevation, the southeast region, sand, hills, and sea clay are positively associated. The results also highlight the importance of considering the entire conditional distribution of groundwater levels, as the relationships between predictors and the response can vary across quantiles. Across all quantiles, the pseudo- R^2 values increase as more predictor variables are added to the model, with Model 5 having the highest pseudo- R^2 values (0.7414128 for the 10th quantile, 0.6127993 for the 25th quantile, and 0.6640333 for the 50th quantile).

A separate section will be dedicated to the results of including interaction terms in Model 5 and including lags for precipitation in the extreme drought case (Model 6).

Table 4: Model Selection Summary of the 2.5th quantile (Extreme drought condition)

	Model 1	Coef.	Model 2	Coef.	Model 3	Coef.	Model 4	Coef.	Model 5	Coef.
Vars.	Intercept	-1.88317***	Intercept	-2.26531***	Intercept	-2.24567***	Intercept	-1.46273***	Intercept	-1.35871***
	Temperature	-0.00145***	Temperature	-0.00160***	Temperature	-0.00164***	Temperature	-0.00139***	Temperature	-0.00130***
	Precipitation	0.00054***	Precipitation	-0.00023	Precipitation	-0.00022	Precipitation	-0.00018	Precipitation	0.00046
	Evaporation	-0.00435***	Evaporation	0.00047	Evaporation	0.00059	Evaporation	-0.00125***	Evaporation	-0.00127***
			Elevation	0.00260***	Elevation	0.00261***	Elevation	0.00221***	Elevation	0.00215***
					Urban	-0.17466	Urban	-0.51347***	Urban	-1.09976***
							Southeast	-0.08282***	Southeast	-0.25013***
							Sand	0.23607***	Sand	0.13214***
							Dune	-0.91517***	Dune	-1.03903***
							Peat land	-7.65426***	Peat	-7.26059***
							Hill	0.39749***	Hill	0.41223***
							River clay	-1.23795***	River clay	-1.28764***
							Sea clay	8.97799***	Sea clay	9.00476***
									Temp:Precip	0.00000***
									Elev:Urban	0.00071***
AIC	10,177,746		9,598,979		9,598,630		9,367,080		9,351,341	
Δ AIC	2,228.033		580,994.8		581,343.5		812,893.6		776,479.2	
R ²	0.874651		0.8953211		0.8953337		0.9033473		0.9037133	

*** p < 0.01 ** p < 0.05 * p < 0.1

Table 5: Model Selection Summary of the 10th quantile

	Model 1	Coef.	Model 2	Coef.	Model 3	Coef.	Model 4	Coef.	Model 5	Coef.
Variables	Intercept	-0.44560***	Intercept	-1.15017***	Intercept	-1.06010***	Intercept	-1.61097***	Intercept	-1.64836***
	Temperature	-0.00176***	Temperature	-0.00173***	Temperature	-0.00164***	Temperature	-0.00152***	Temperature	-0.00144***
	Precipitation	0.00077***	Precipitation	0.00032***	Precipitation	0.00032***	Precipitation	0.00035***	Precipitation	0.00096***
	Evaporation	-0.00151***	Evaporation	-0.00109***	Evaporation	-0.00106***	Evaporation	-0.00028	Evaporation	-0.00019
			Elevation	0.00437***	Elevation	0.00442***	Elevation	0.00420***	Elevation	0.00423***
					Urban	-0.60054***	Urban	-0.72517***	Urban	-0.57197***
							Southeast	0.35577***	Southeast	0.36371***
							Sand	1.14766***	Sand	1.16420***
							Dune	0.05585***	Dune	0.08439***
							Peat land	-1.06022***	Peat	-1.04693***
							Hill	0.85980***	Hill	0.86897***
							River clay	-0.83738***	River clay	-0.78842***
							Sea clay	7.30352***	Sea clay	7.33351***
									Temp:Precip	0.00000***
									Elev:Urban	-0.00028***
	AIC	9,838,615		8,725,285		8,715,099		8,562,673		8,557,301
Δ AIC	2,318.79		1,115,649		1,125,835		1,278,261		1,231,735	
R ²	0.6059885348		0.7264450		0.7274020		0.7413277		0.7414128	

*** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1

Table 6: Model Selection Summary of the 25th quantile

	Model 1	Coef.	Model 2	Coef.	Model 3	Coef.	Model 4	Coef.	Model 5	Coef.
Variables	Intercept	1.84254***	Intercept	-0.65208***	Intercept	-0.53083***	Intercept	-1.18842***	Intercept	-1.24331***
	Temperature	-0.00358***	Temperature	-0.00161***	Temperature	-0.00158***	Temperature	-0.00175***	Temperature	-0.00171***
	Precipitation	0.00156***	Precipitation	0.00030***	Precipitation	0.00034***	Precipitation	0.00036***	Precipitation	0.00126***
	Evaporation	0.00209***	Evaporation	-0.00097***	Evaporation	-0.00065***	Evaporation	0.00018	Evaporation	0.00034***
			Elevation	0.00669***	Elevation	0.00681***	Elevation	0.00658***	Elevation	0.00670***
					Urban	-1.09019***	Urban	-1.14618***	Urban	-0.75869***
							Southeast	0.31257***	Southeast	0.31601***
							Sand	1.06088***	Sand	1.05448***
							Dune	0.34740***	Dune	0.37149***
							Peat land	-0.22233***	Peat	-0.20868***
							Hill	0.87079***	Hill	0.86146***
							River clay	-1.18855***	River clay	-1.16416***
							Sea clay	5.03158***	Sea clay	4.92300***
									Temp:Precip	-0.00001***
									Elev:Urban	-0.00073***
	AIC	9,921,451		8,008,139		7,975,219		7,853,482		7,843,204
Δ AIC	2,183.107		1,915,495		1,948,415		2,070,152		2,026,275	
R ²	0.2236924444		0.5907848		0.5953927		0.6119877		0.6127993	

*** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1

Table 7: Model Selection Summary of the 50th quantile (Median)

	Model 1	Coef.	Model 2	Coef.	Model 3	Coef.	Model 4	Coef.	Model 5	Coef.
Variables	Intercept	6.63233***	Intercept	-0.48983***	Intercept	-0.37689***	Intercept	-0.46180***	Intercept	-0.62692***
	Temperature	-0.00391***	Temperature	-0.00195***	Temperature	-0.00192***	Temperature	-0.00199***	Temperature	-0.00187***
	Precipitation	0.00156***	Precipitation	0.00046***	Precipitation	0.00045***	Precipitation	0.00046***	Precipitation	0.00237***
	Evaporation	0.00094	Evaporation	-0.00046***	Evaporation	-0.00047***	Evaporation	-0.00060***	Evaporation	-0.00003
			Elevation	0.00892***	Elevation	0.00895***	Elevation	0.00886***	Elevation	0.00902***
					Urban	-1.10061***	Urban	-1.10058***	Urban	-0.31506***
							Southeast	0.09054***	Southeast	0.08526***
							Sand	0.14385***	Sand	0.18340***
							Dune	-0.00869***	Dune	0.06176***
							Peat land	-0.07352***	Peat	0.01792***
							Hill	0.23123***	Hill	0.27214***
							River clay	-0.81306***	River clay	-0.77952***
							Sea clay	1.59818***	Sea clay	1.49337***
									Temp:Precip	-0.00001***
									Elev:Urban	-0.00134***
	AIC	10,187,534		7,100,604		7,037,698		6,999,866		6,962,966
Δ AIC	1,903,939		3,088,834		3,151,740		3,189,572		3,169,567	
R ²	0.0006535459		0.6482178		0.6557482		0.6602008		0.6640333	

*** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1

4.3 Model 1

The climate variables introduced in Section 3, including temperature, precipitation, and evaporation, are included in Model 1 to estimate their relationships with groundwater levels across all years. The results indicate that these climate variables play a significant role in explaining groundwater drought conditions at the 2.5th percentile. Temperature and evaporation have negative effects, suggesting that higher values are associated with lower groundwater levels in the lower tail of the distribution. Precipitation, on the other hand, has a positive effect, with a coefficient of 0.00054, implying that increased rainfall is linked to higher groundwater levels at the 2.5th percentile.

4.4 Model 2

The results of Model 2 reveal that elevation has a significant positive effect on groundwater levels. This means that groundwater levels tend to be higher in areas with greater elevation. Consistent with topographic influences, higher groundwater levels are typically observed in elevated regions. This finding aligns with existing literature on mountain hydrogeology (Somers and McKenzie, 2020). Groundwater processes in mountainous regions differ substantially from those in lower relief areas due to three main factors. Firstly, mountain regions typically have higher water table positions and steeper hydraulic gradients, which significantly influence local flow paths and discharge rates. Secondly, the near-surface hydrogeologic stratigraphy in these areas is often highly complex, resulting from high-energy depositional environments and glacial processes (Somers and McKenzie, 2020). Lastly, the pronounced surface topography in mountainous areas drives deeper groundwater circulation, contributing to the recharge of regional and even continental-scale flow systems. This deeper circulation can potentially allow the geothermal temperature gradient to affect groundwater flow patterns (Somers and McKenzie, 2020).

While higher elevations may generally correlate with increased groundwater levels relative to the Normaal Amsterdams Peil (NAP), these levels are often found deeper below the surface, making them more challenging to water users and vegetation to access. Additionally, in the Netherlands, higher elevated areas typically have more sandy soils. Consequently, in areas with low precipitation, higher-elevation regions may be more vulnerable to drought conditions due to the difficulty in reaching these groundwater resources. It is therefore important to estimate the model with land use and geology type effects to capture the potential interactions between these factors and climate variables in influencing groundwater levels during droughts. Areas with higher elevations and well-draining soils may be more resilient to groundwater drought, as suggested by the positive association between elevation, sand, and sea clay soils with higher groundwater levels at the 2.5th percentile. However, elevated regions that rely primarily on precipitation for groundwater recharge could still be susceptible to prolonged dry periods, especially if they have limited water storage capacity or are located in rain shadows. Incorporating land use and geology information allows the model to account for these nuances and provides a more comprehensive understanding of how topography, climate, and local conditions jointly influence groundwater drought vulnerability across different regions.

4.5 Model 3

The addition of the urban dummy variable in Model 3 shows that groundwater levels in cities tend to be lower compared to non-urban areas at the 2.5th percentile. This may be due to higher water consumption and reduced land availability for groundwater recharge in urban areas, or because cities are often built on less swampy areas that naturally support groundwater recharge.

Additionally, urban development alter the natural hydrology of an area, affecting groundwater recharge and discharge patterns. Changes in surface water drainage, soil compaction, and the construction of underground infrastructure can disrupt the natural movement of water and impact groundwater levels. The inclusion of more land use dummies may cover the impact of these effects.

The inclusion of a dummy variable for the southeastern region reveals a significant positive effect on groundwater levels at the 2.5th percentile. The elevated topography of the southeast likely contributes to these higher groundwater levels through increased precipitation, unique geological characteristics that favor water retention, and potentially different land use patterns or reduced extraction rates. Despite being situated at a higher elevation, which typically makes areas more susceptible to drought, the southeastern region maintains relatively higher groundwater levels even during drought conditions (2.5th percentile). This suggests that topography plays a crucial role in groundwater dynamics, potentially providing a buffer against extreme drought impacts in this region. However, it's important to note that while levels may be higher, the area's reliance on precipitation for groundwater recharge could still make it vulnerable to prolonged drought periods.

4.6 Model 4

Model 4 incorporates temperature, precipitation, evaporation, elevation, urban areas, the southeast region, and the six dummies for various soil types. The results indicate that, in line with the results of Model 1, temperature and evaporation have significant negative effects on groundwater levels during drought conditions. Elevation and certain soil types, such as sand and sea clay, are positively associated with higher groundwater levels at the 2.5th percentile relative to the NAP. However, this relationship is more complex than it initially appears. In the Netherlands, while higher elevated areas have higher groundwater levels relative to the NAP, they are paradoxically more prone to drought. This is because these areas often experience faster drainage, which translates into less recharge. As a result, despite having higher groundwater levels relative to NAP, these elevated areas with well-draining soils may actually be more vulnerable to groundwater drought.

In contrast, urban areas, dunes, peat, and river clay soils are linked to lower groundwater levels, likely due to factors such as reduced recharge, higher water consumption, and altered hydrology. However, some of these areas, particularly those with clay and peat soils, may retain water more effectively, potentially offering better resilience against drought despite their lower elevation and lower groundwater levels relative to NAP.

The southeast region shows a negative coefficient in contrast to the other quantiles, where the southeast dummy has a positive coefficient. This indicates that groundwater levels in this area tend to be lower compared to other regions in the extreme drought case, even after accounting for differences in climate, elevation, and soil characteristics. This finding suggests that there may be additional regional factors, such as groundwater extraction patterns or hydrogeological conditions, that contribute to lower groundwater levels in the southeast.

4.7 Model 5

Model 5 builds upon previous models by incorporating interaction terms, enhancing our understanding of how various factors jointly influence groundwater levels during extreme drought conditions (2.5th quantile). The results indicate that climate variables continue to play a significant role. Temperature (-0.00130) and evaporation (-0.00127) have negative effects, suggesting that higher values are associated with lower groundwater levels. In contrast, precipitation (0.00046) shows a positive but statistically insignificant effect, indicating limited impact on groundwater levels at this percentile.

The interaction terms reveal important dynamics. The temperature-precipitation interaction suggests a minimal increase in the effect of precipitation on groundwater levels with higher temperatures. This indicates that while higher temperatures generally reduce groundwater levels, they may also enhance the effectiveness of precipitation in replenishing groundwater, albeit minimally.

Additionally, the elevation-urban interaction (0.00071) implies that the negative impact of urbanization on groundwater levels is somewhat mitigated at higher elevations. This suggests that higher elevations might offer better drainage and groundwater recharge, even in urbanized areas.

Interestingly, under extreme drought conditions, the coefficient for precipitation changes from negative to positive, which could be attributed to the interaction terms. This shift indicates that while precipitation alone might not significantly impact groundwater levels during droughts, its combined effect with other variables, such as temperature and urbanization, can lead to a more positive influence.

4.8 Model 6

Table 8: Regression Results for Different Time Lags

Variable	2 Weeks	1 Month	3 Months	6 Months	1 Year
(Intercept)	-1.34743***	-1.34889***	-1.36164***	-1.37994***	-1.41681***
temperature	-0.00131***	-0.00127***	-0.00130***	-0.00122***	-0.00140***
precipitation_lag	-0.00035***	-0.00040***	-0.00062***	-0.00063***	-0.00045***
evaporation	-0.00138***	-0.00147***	-0.00117***	-0.00182***	-0.00145***
elevation_values	0.00215***	0.00215***	0.00214***	0.00213***	0.00212***
urban	-1.09107***	-1.08495***	-1.04525***	-0.98998***	-0.88234***
is_southeast	-0.24707***	-0.24448***	-0.23327***	-0.20701***	-0.13729***
is_sand	0.13514***	0.13902***	0.16074***	0.19441***	0.26870***
is_dune	-1.03814***	-1.03713***	-1.02711***	-1.01696***	-0.97716***
is_peat	-7.26501***	-7.25980***	-7.28489***	-7.32966***	-7.42081***
is_hill	0.41245***	0.41333***	0.42043***	0.42276***	0.42487***
is_riverclay	-1.28129***	-1.28085***	-1.26653***	-1.23444***	-1.16378***
is_seaclay	9.00268***	8.99765***	8.98615***	8.95625***	8.89756***
temperature:precipitation	0.00000**	0.00000***	0.00000**	0.00000	0.00000
elevation_values:urban	0.00071***	0.00071***	0.00070***	0.00068***	0.00065***

- *** $p < 0.01$,
- ** $p < 0.05$,
- * $p < 0.1$

The results of the models with the lagged precipitation are displayed in a separate table, Table 8.

Firstly, the model focuses on the lower extremes of groundwater levels (2.5th quantile), representing extreme drought conditions or periods of low water availability. In this context, the negative relationship could indicate that during periods of low groundwater levels, recent precipitation (lagged by two weeks) has not yet had a positive impact on groundwater recharge. This could be due to factors such as high evaporation rates, runoff, or the time required for water to percolate through the soil and reach the aquifer. Additionally, in some geological settings, there might be a delay longer than two weeks before precipitation significantly affects groundwater levels, especially in deeper aquifers or areas with less permeable soils. Therefore, the model is estimated with more lags as well.

The coefficient for the precipitation lagged by one month also shows a negative relationship with groundwater levels at this extreme quantile. This suggests that a one-month lag may not be sufficient for precipitation to positively impact groundwater levels, especially during extreme drought conditions. In such scenarios, recent precipitation might be absorbed by the dry soil or lost to evaporation before it can percolate down to the aquifer. Additionally, dry soil conditions often lead to increased runoff, which further reduces the amount of water available for groundwater recharge.

All models at the 2.5th percentile with different precipitation lags show significant negative relationships between lagged precipitation and groundwater levels. The negative impact of precipitation on extreme low groundwater levels is strongest at 3-6 months lag. This suggests that during periods of extreme low groundwater levels, the effects of precipitation are not immediately apparent and may take several months to influence groundwater recharge. This delayed effect could be due to the time required for water to infiltrate through the soil and reach the groundwater table, particularly in regions with deep aquifers or low soil permeability.

5 Discussion

This study provides insights into the factors influencing groundwater levels in the Netherlands, particularly under extreme drought conditions. This nuanced understanding enhances our knowledge of groundwater dynamics and contributes to the broader field of hydrology by highlighting the importance of considering relationships and interactions among variables. One significant contribution of this thesis is its focus on QR, which allows for a more detailed exploration of the relationships between predictors and groundwater levels, particularly in extreme conditions. This approach contrasts with traditional methods that often assume uniform effects across the entire distribution of groundwater levels.

Comparing the results with previous studies reveals both consistency and new insights. For instance, the findings on the negative impact of temperature on groundwater levels align with the study by [Amanambu et al. \(2020\)](#), who also found that increasing temperatures lead to lower groundwater levels due to increased evapotranspiration. How-

ever, this study provides a more detailed understanding of how ? the relationships vary across different quantiles, which is a valuable contribution to the field.

The results of this thesis on the impact of soil types on groundwater levels add nuance to previous findings. While studies like [Brakkee et al. \(2022\)](#) have highlighted the importance of geology in groundwater responses to climate, this quantile regression approach reveals how these relationships can vary under different groundwater conditions, particularly during droughts.

[Witte et al. \(2019\)](#) found that changes in land use, particularly the transition from heathland to agricultural land and forest, have substantially reduced groundwater recharge. Increased agricultural activity led to higher water consumption by crops, further diminishing the amount of water available for groundwater replenishment. The study quantifies this reduction in recharge at approximately 100 mm/year, resulting in an average groundwater level decline of 0.3 meters across the province of Noord Brabant, with some areas experiencing declines of up to 1 meter.

Connecting these findings to the observed negative coefficient for groundwater levels in Noord Brabant, which lies in the southeast region of the Netherlands, it becomes evident that similar factors may be contributing to the lower groundwater levels in this area. The southeast region, characterized by its agricultural practices, may be experiencing analogous land use changes and increased water extraction, leading to reduced groundwater recharge. The study highlights the importance of considering regional factors, such as land use and groundwater extraction patterns, in understanding groundwater dynamics. Having series of groundwater extractions could potentially improve the QR models.

The findings from Model 5 align with broader insights from groundwater management literature. For instance, the thematic papers on groundwater management emphasize the importance of understanding how various factors, including climate variables and land use changes, interact to influence groundwater resources. The negative impacts of urbanization and elevation on groundwater levels, as identified in Model 5, are consistent with observations that urban landscapes significantly alter hydrological processes, affecting both infiltration and evapotranspiration ([Salvadore et al., 2015](#); [McGrane, 2016](#)). These changes make it challenging to accurately quantify groundwater dynamics across diverse landscapes at varying scales.

The temperature-precipitation interaction observed in Model 5 also resonates with findings from groundwater management strategies that highlight how higher temperatures can increase evapotranspiration rates, thereby reducing the amount of precipitation that actually recharges groundwater ([Le et al., 2021](#)). This interaction term helps model how temperature modifies the effectiveness of precipitation in replenishing groundwater, especially under varying seasonal dynamics. For instance, winter precipitation might be more effective for groundwater recharge in colder climates where evaporation is lower. During drought periods, high temperatures can exacerbate the effects of low precipitation on groundwater levels, and the interaction term allows the model to account for this compounding effect.

The results of Model 6 suggest that extreme low groundwater levels are influenced by long-term precipitation patterns (3-6 months prior) more than recent rainfall. The negative relationship might indicate that during extreme dry periods, recent precipitation

is not sufficient to recharge groundwater levels significantly. This delayed response and the importance of long-term precipitation patterns align with the findings of [Van Loon et al. \(2017\)](#), who observed strong spatial differences in groundwater response times to meteorological inputs. [Van Loon et al. \(2017\)](#) found that optimal accumulation periods for groundwater response ranged from 1 to over 24 months, highlighting the complex and spatially variable nature of groundwater systems. This thesis' results are largely consistent with this finding, as significant impacts of precipitation lags up to 6 months are identified. However, this study's focus on extreme low groundwater levels (2.5th quantile) provides specific insights into the behavior of groundwater systems during drought conditions.

Furthermore, different modeling approaches have been used in the literature to capture the lagged effects of precipitation on groundwater response. For instance, [Le et al. \(2021\)](#) employed a vector autoregression (VAR) model to analyze the relationship between precipitation and groundwater levels in the Vietnamese Mekong Delta. Their study used annual time-series data, they de-trended the variables to remove climate change effects, and applied lags of up to 4 years. This approach also demonstrates the importance of considering multi-year lag effects in certain hydrogeological settings.

Like this study, many other studies, such as [Wada et al. \(2010\)](#) and [Le et al. \(2021\)](#) have also shown a delay between precipitation and groundwater response. For example, in areas with highly permeable soils, such as sandy soils, groundwater levels may respond to precipitation within a few days to a week. This rapid response is due to the quick infiltration and percolation of water through the soil profile. Studies have shown that groundwater levels can exhibit significant changes shortly after precipitation events, especially in regions with shallow aquifers and high soil permeability. On the other hand, research indicates that groundwater levels in areas with less permeable soils may show a more gradual response to cumulative precipitation over a season, reflecting the time needed for water to move through the soil and recharge the aquifer ([Le et al., 2021](#); [Wada et al., 2010](#)).

6 Limitations and further research suggestions

There are several limitations and areas for improvement that future research could address. One limitation is the use of the LGN2022 dataset for land use, which represents only a single point in time rather than the entire 2002-2024 analysis period. Since [Witte et al. \(2019\)](#) stated that land use changes could potentially influence groundwater levels, future studies could employ a land use change model to more accurately represent land use dynamics throughout the study period, potentially revealing important temporal trends in the relationship between land use and groundwater levels.

While the model incorporates a range of climatic, geographical, and soil factors, there is the potential to include additional explanatory variables, such as population density, groundwater extraction rates, irrigation practices, or more detailed climate indices. These could provide more direct insight into human impacts on groundwater levels, as suggested by [Wada et al. \(2010\)](#) in their global analysis of groundwater depletion. [Wada et al. \(2010\)](#)

demonstrated the critical role of human activities, particularly groundwater abstraction for irrigation, in driving global groundwater depletion. They emphasized the need to consider both natural and anthropogenic factors in assessing groundwater resources. By incorporating similar variables in this thesis' QR model, the complex interplay between human activities and natural processes in shaping groundwater dynamics in the Netherlands could potentially be captured. For instance, time series of groundwater extraction could be very useful.

The current study uses a pooled model approach, which assumes homogeneity across wells. Given the large panel dataset, incorporating fixed effects could account for unobserved heterogeneity across wells, potentially reducing uncertainty in the model. Future research could explore the implementation of a Fixed Effects Quantile Regression (FE QR) model for a more detailed analysis, following the approach of [Canay \(2011\)](#) in panel data quantile regression. The FE QR could identify more drivers of groundwater drought.

While the model in this thesis focuses on shorter-term lags for precipitation (up to one year), it is important to acknowledge that longer-term lags could play a significant role in groundwater dynamics. As stated earlier, future studies could potentially incorporate these extended lag periods to capture the full spectrum of delayed groundwater responses to precipitation events. Additionally, the choice of lag period should be carefully considered based on the specific hydrogeological characteristics of the study area and the temporal resolution of available data.

The current models assume linear relationships between predictors and the response variable. Incorporating non-linear terms or transformations of predictors could capture potential non-linear effects and improve the model fit, particularly for variables like temperature or precipitation, which may have complex, non-linear relationships with groundwater levels. This approach has been successfully applied in other hydrological studies, such as [Kisi \(2015\)](#), where non-linear models provided a better understanding of the intricate relationships between climatic variables and hydrological responses.

The use of yearly dummies in the model, while informative, may not capture the full complexity of temporal effects on groundwater levels. Future analysis could consider creating separate dummies for different seasons or employing more flexible temporal structures, such as splines or polynomials, to better capture non-linear and seasonal effects of drought on groundwater levels.

Overall, while this study provides insight into the factors influencing groundwater levels in the Netherlands, there are numerous opportunities for future research to build upon and refine these findings. By addressing the limitations and expanding the scope of the analysis, future studies can contribute to an even better understanding of groundwater dynamics.

7 Conclusion

This study employed quantile regression (QR) to identify the key drivers of groundwater drought in the Netherlands and assess how their impacts differ across the groundwater level distribution and spatially across the country. The QR models revealed that temper-

ature, evaporation, elevation, urban areas, geographic regions, lagged precipitation, the interaction terms and soil types are significant predictors of groundwater levels during extreme drought conditions.

A key finding of this research is the variability in the magnitude and direction of these drivers' effects, which vary depending on the groundwater level quantile analyzed. This variability shows the importance of considering the entire conditional distribution of groundwater levels when developing management strategies. For instance, under extreme drought conditions (2.5th quantile), temperature and urban areas have strong negative impacts, while elevation, sand, and sea clay soils are positively associated with higher groundwater levels. The difference in signs throughout the different quantiles for certain variables like the southeast region underscores this importance.

The QR approach provides a more nuanced understanding of how climate, landscape, and human factors interact to influence groundwater availability under varying drought severities. This insight allows for the development of adaptive, location-specific management plans that can respond effectively to changing climate conditions and weather patterns. By considering the entire lower tail of the distribution of groundwater levels rather than just the mean, this approach offers a more robust foundation for decision-making in water resource management.

The analysis reveals that groundwater levels in the southeastern region tend to be lower compared to other areas at the extreme lower quantile, even after accounting for differences in climate, elevation, and soil characteristics. This suggests that there may be additional regional factors contributing to the vulnerability of groundwater resources in the southeast during drought conditions, such as higher rates of groundwater extraction, unique hydrogeological conditions that limit recharge, or other unobserved regional characteristics. To further investigate these regional differences and capture unobserved heterogeneity, future research could employ a fixed effects quantile regression (FEQR) model, which incorporates well-specific fixed effects to provide a more robust analysis of the factors influencing groundwater drought in the southeast region while taking into account both observed and unobserved regional differences.

Based on the findings of this study, several key recommendations emerge for policymakers to effectively manage groundwater resources. Firstly, land use planning should be informed by a thorough understanding of soil types and geological features. Areas with soil and geological characteristics that positively influence groundwater levels, such as sand and sea clay soils, should be prioritized for conservation efforts. Conversely, in regions where soil types negatively impact groundwater levels, like peat land and river clay areas, additional measures may be necessary to enhance groundwater recharge. This targeted approach ensures that conservation and development efforts are strategically aligned with the natural characteristics of the land.

Secondly, groundwater management strategies should be tailored to local topographical and regional characteristics rather than adopting a one-size-fits-all approach. The positive relationship between elevation and groundwater levels demonstrates the importance of considering topography in water source management. Policies should recognize the varying impacts of factors like temperature, urban areas, and soil types on groundwater levels across different regions and elevations. [Witte et al. \(2023\)](#) suggested that for

densely populated regions characterized by competing interests, it is crucial to acknowledge that maintaining historical practices in agriculture may not always be feasible or desirable. Adaptation strategies must be considered and implemented where necessary. One such adaptive measure to mitigate drought-related damages involves promoting vegetation with lower evapotranspiration requirements. This way, water resource managers can potentially improve the resilience of groundwater systems to drought conditions

Thirdly, the significant influence of temperature on groundwater levels highlights the urgent need for policies that prepare for and mitigate the impacts of climate change on water resources. Policymakers should prioritize the development and implementation of climate adaptation strategies to protect groundwater resources in the face of rising temperatures. These strategies should be based on a comprehensive understanding of how climate variables interact with other factors to affect groundwater availability under varying drought conditions. Additionally, the significance of regional factors in the model results suggests that effective groundwater management requires cooperation between different regions. Policymakers should foster inter-regional collaboration to ensure a coordinated approach to groundwater management. This collaboration should involve data sharing, joint planning, and the implementation of consistent policies across jurisdictions.

Lastly, the importance of data-driven decision-making cannot be overstated. Investments should be made in systems to track the various factors influencing groundwater levels, including climate variables, land use changes, and geological characteristics. This data would provide a solid foundation for informed policy decisions and allow for the development of adaptive management strategies that respond to changing conditions over time.

By prioritizing these recommendations, policymakers can develop more targeted, efficient, and adaptive strategies for groundwater conservation and management. This approach will help ensure the long-term sustainability of groundwater resources in the face of growing demands and climate change challenges.

References

- Abbas, S. A. and Xuan, Y. (2019). Development of a new quantile-based method for the assessment of regional water resources in a highly-regulated river basin. *Water Resources Management*, 33:3187–3210. Received: 11 September 2017 / Accepted: 19 May 2019 / Published online: 10 June 2019.
- Abbas, S. A., Xuan, Y., and Song, X. (2019). Quantile regression based methods for investigating rainfall trends associated with flooding and drought conditions. *Water Resources Management*, 33:4249–4264. Received: 1 December 2017 / Accepted: 20 September 2019 / Published online: 28 October 2019.
- Akaike, H. (1973). *Information theory and an extension of the maximum likelihood principle*. Akadémiai Kiadó, Budapest.

- Amanambu, A., Obarein, O., Mossa, J., Li, L., Ayeni, S., Balogun, O., Oyebamiji, A., and Ochege, F. (2020). Groundwater system and climate change: Present status and future considerations. *Journal of Hydrology*, 589:125163.
- Bartholomeus, R. P., van der Wiel, K., van Loon, A. F., van Huijgevoort, M. H., van Vliet, M. T., Mens, M., van Geffen, S. M., Wanders, N., and Pot, W. (2023). Managing water across the flood–drought spectrum: Experiences from and challenges for the netherlands. *Cambridge University Press*. Published online by Cambridge University Press: 30 May 2023.
- Brakkee, E., Van Huijgevoort, M. H., and Bartholomeus, R. P. (2022). Improved understanding of regional groundwater drought development through time series modelling: the 2018–2019 drought in the netherlands. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 26(3):551–569.
- Canay, I. A. (2011). A simple approach to quantile regression for panel data. *The Econometrics Journal*, 14(3):368–386.
- Chen, Y., Zhang, Y., Tian, J., Tang, Z., Wang, L., and Yang, X. (2024). Understanding the propagation of meteorological drought to groundwater drought: A case study of the north china plain. *Water*, 16(3):501. Submission received: 10 January 2024 / Revised: 27 January 2024 / Accepted: 1 February 2024 / Published: 4 February 2024.
- DINoloket (2023). Ondergrondmodellen. <https://www.dinoloket.nl/oondergrondmodellen/kaart>. Accessed: 2023-06-12.
- El Bouazzaoui, I., Lamhour, O., Ait Brahim, Y., Najmi, A., and Bougadir, B. (2024). Three decades of groundwater drought research: Evolution and trends. *Water*, 16:743.
- Graham, B. S., Hahn, J., Poirier, A., and Powell, J. L. (2015). Quantile regression with panel data. (21034).
- Guermazi, E., Milano, M., Reynard, E., and Zairi, M. (2019). Impact of climate change and anthropogenic pressure on the groundwater resources in arid environment. *Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change*, 24.
- Hiemstra, P. and Sluiter, R. (2011). Interpolation of makkink evaporation in the netherlands. Technical Report TR-327, Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute (KNMI).
- IPCC (2022). *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA.
- Karunakalage, A., Lee, J.-Y., Daqiq, M. T., Cha, J., Jang, J., and Kannaujiya, S. (2024). Characterization of groundwater drought and understanding of climatic impact on groundwater resources in korea. *Journal of Hydrology*, 634:131014.

- Kisi, O. (2015). Streamflow forecasting and estimation using least square support vector regression and adaptive neuro-fuzzy embedded fuzzy c-means clustering. *Water Resources Management*, 29(15):5109–5127.
- KNMI (2023). Waarnemingen - KNMI. <https://www.knmi.nl/nederland-nu/weer/waarnemingen>. Accessed: 2024-05-31.
- Koenker, R. (2005). *Quantile regression*. Cambridge university press.
- Koenker, R. and Bassett Jr, G. (1978). Regression quantiles. *Econometrica*, 46(1):33–50.
- Koenker, R. and Machado, J. A. (1999). Goodness of fit and related inference processes for quantile regression. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 94(448):1296–1310.
- Le, P. V. V., Pham, H. V., Bui, L. K., Tran, A. N., Pham, C. V., Nguyen, G. V., and Tran, P. A. (2021). Responses of groundwater to precipitation variability and ENSO in the vietnamese mekong delta. *Hydrological Research*, 52(6):1280–1296.
- Learbuch, K., Smidt, H., and van der Wielen, P. (2022). Water and biofilm in drinking water distribution systems in the netherlands. *KWR Water Research Institute, Laboratory of Microbiology, Wageningen University & Research*. Received 25 January 2022, Revised 26 March 2022, Accepted 27 March 2022, Available online 30 March 2022, Version of Record 5 April 2022.
- Li, G., Li, Y., and Tsai, C.-L. (2015). Quantile correlations and quantile autoregressive modeling. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 110(509):246–261.
- McGrane, S. J. (2016). Impacts of urbanisation on hydrological and water quality dynamics, and urban water management: a review. *Hydrological Sciences Journal*, 61(13):2295–2311.
- Nygren, M., Barthel, R., Allen, D. M., and Giese, M. (2022). Exploring groundwater drought responsiveness in lowland post-glacial environments. *Hydrogeology Journal*, 30(7):1937–1961.
- Philip, S. Y., Kew, S. F., van der Wiel, K., Wanders, N., and van Oldenborgh, G. J. (2020). Regional differentiation in climate change induced drought trends in the netherlands. *Environmental Research Letters*, 15(9):094081.
- Pronk, G. J., Stoffberg, S. F., Van Dooren, T. C. G. W., Groenendijk, P., Bartholomeus, R. P., and Van der Grift, B. (2021). Increasing water system robustness in the netherlands: Potential of cross-sectoral water reuse. *Water Resources Management*, 35:3721–3735.
- Salvadore, E., Bronders, J., and Batelaan, O. (2015). Hydrological modelling of urbanized catchments: A review and future directions. *Journal of Hydrology*, 529:1–12.

- Samaniego, L., Thober, S., Kumar, R., et al. (2018). Anthropogenic warming exacerbates european soil moisture droughts. *Nature Climate Change*, 8:421–426.
- Schmidheiny, K. (2021). Panel data: Fixed and random effects. Handout.
- Schreiner-McGraw, A. P. and Ajami, H. (2021). Delayed response of groundwater to multi-year meteorological droughts in the absence of anthropogenic management. *Journal of Hydrology*, 603:126917.
- Shin, W., Kim, M., and Jung, Y. (2022). Efficient information-based criteria for model selection in quantile regression. *Journal of the Korean Statistical Society*, 51:245–281.
- Somers, L. D. and McKenzie, J. M. (2020). A review of groundwater in high mountain environments. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Water*, 7(6):e1475.
- Srinivasulu, A., Lal, A., and Naidu, R. (2024). A critical review of climate change impacts on groundwater resources: A focus on the current status, future possibilities, and role of simulation models. *Atmosphere*, 15(1):122.
- Statistics Netherlands (2020). How do we use our land? [Online; accessed 03-June-2024].
- Tareghian, R. and Rasmussen, P. (2013). Statistical downscaling of precipitation using quantile regression. *Journal of Hydrology*, 487:122–135.
- Taylor, R. G., Scanlon, B., D'oll, P., Rodell, M., Van Beek, R., Wada, Y., Longuevergne, L., Leblanc, M., Famiglietti, J. S., Edmunds, M., et al. (2013). Ground water and climate change. *Nature Climate Change*, 3(4):322–329.
- Toreti, A., Belward, A., Perez-Dominguez, I., Naumann, G., Luterbacher, J., Cronie, O., Seguini, L., Manfron, G., Lopez-Lozano, R., et al. (2019). The exceptional 2018 european water seesaw calls for action on adaptation. *Earth's Future*. First published: 15 May 2019.
- Van Loon, A. F., Kumar, R., and Mishra, V. (2017). Testing the use of standardised indices and grace satellite data to estimate the european 2015 groundwater drought in near-real time. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 21:1947–1971.
- Verburg, P. H., Soepboer, W., Veldkamp, A., Limpiada, R., Espaldon, V., and Mastura, S. S. (2002). Modeling the spatial dynamics of regional land use: the clue-s model. *Environmental Management*, 30:391–405.
- Villarini, G., Smith, J. A., Baeck, M. L., and Krajewski, W. F. (2011). Examining flood frequency distributions in the midwest u.s. *Journal of the American Water Resources Association*, 47(3):447–463.
- Vincenty, T. (1975). Direct and inverse solutions of geodesics on the ellipsoid with application of nested equations. *Survey review*, 23(176):88–93.

- Wada, Y., van Beek, L. P. H., van Kempen, C. M., Reckman, J. W. T. M., Vasak, S., and Bierkens, M. F. P. (2010). Global depletion of groundwater resources. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 37(20):L20402.
- Witte, J.-P., van den Eertwegh, G. A., and van Deijl, D. (2023). Met graan meer grondwater: Hoe op hoger gelegen zandgronden de landbouw zich kan aanpassen aan droge zomers. *Water Governance*, 1:48–57.
- Witte, J.-P. M., Zaadnoordijk, W. J., and Buyse, J. J. (2019). Forensic hydrology reveals why groundwater tables in the province of noord brabant (the netherlands) dropped more than expected. *Water*, 12(5):1401.